

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FRINWIE****FIRST NAME: LOVELINE MUMA****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper intends to draw attention on writing a good academic paper base on essential concepts of academic writing by analyzing the course pack mainly from chapters 1-5. ACA-401D period one focuses on writing a good academic paper that can be published and recognized at international levels. The course pack emphasizes on essential concepts of academic writing and clearly outline rules, principles, and styles of writing a good essay as well as academic papers for publishing. Specifically, chapters 1 to 5 of the course pack is very explicit, chapter one gives detail guides on how to start an essay and researching an essay topic. chapter two explains what plagiarism is and elaborating on why it is bad as well as convincing writers to always give credit to an author of a write up (EUCLID 2019, 5).

Chapter three talks about some rules of thumb for writing papers. Chapter four focuses on literature review and chapter five focuses on what is style guide and why it is important to use one. Period one includes a video on basic ACA-401 Tutorials. The video teaches how to use a style in word, Response Paper (RP) template, US and UK English in spellings, referencing the text and material as well as how to do citations.

2) REACTION TO CHAPTERS 1-2 FOR A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER

Starting an essay or academic paper used to be my challenge but I noticed in this study material that when I start writing early it cuts down on anxiety beats procrastination and gives me time to develop my ideas appropriately. In this part, I realized that there are a lot of points to be taken into consideration when writing an academic paper. Some of the concepts that attracted my attention are those of starting an essay that entails time, reading, researching, thinking as well as construction of an initial plan, which is connected to a topic or question (EUCLID 2019, 1). Essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking which could be a reality that helps broadens ideas of the writer like myself.

I like to argue that even though plagiarism has been a bad practice writers seem to have challenges of dealing with it which is probably one of the reasons that it seems to always be a point of focus and warning to researchers not to practice it. In chapter two, the writer talks on plagiarism concept with emphasis on giving credit to the author of the source of information. Giving credit to the author is “When using quote, paraphrase statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is burrowed from another source” (EUCLID 2019, 5). The course material has given me an in-depth understanding on the importance of giving credits to other authors’ work.

When I wrote my first research paper, I was given a failed mark because I did not give credit to the author of parts of the material I used in my academic paper. The emphasis in the study material to give credits to author further reminds me of how bad and offensive it is to practice plagiarism when writing an academic paper. When writing a good academic paper, citing through in-text citation and list of works cited will avoid plagiarism. (EUCLID 2019, 6). It is very crucial to use academic styles and there is more to apply about citations depending on whether the paper is an independent paper or response paper or midterm paper. With the practice of styles and not using plagiarism there is weight to the researchers work as well as keen attention to who is reading the work.

3) REACTIONS TO CHAPTER 3-5 FOR A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER

In chapter three, some rules of thumb for writing papers with key points have been elaborated. These include: stating the main thesis in the opening paragraph; remain focused by guiding the write-up by particular problems that animate the paper; do not conclude with generalities; write clearly; try to use stylistic variety and do not make the writing boring and clumsy. Quote a passage if it plays an important role in the paper thereby supporting assertions as well as take views of discussions seriously (EUCLID 2019, 15).

Chapter four gives a sense of direction on key important reminders on how to use punctuation marks, which could sometimes be very challenging when writing academic papers. Chapter five is about the style guide. My intake from this chapter is that a good

academic paper must follow a particular guide. I have learned some rules in writing academic papers and that EUCLID specifically recommends Chicago rules (Turabian) and requires students to download the template, Euclid guidelines as well as using American English for EUCLID papers.

4) CONCLUSION

Academic papers are a way of writers or researchers to express their views, disciplines and expertise. This also requires the writer to attract the interest of the readers in the academic paper. This will be greatly enhanced by the use of required styles, citations, and giving credits to the work of authors used. A paper in which plagiarism is not practiced always encourages publishers to publish it and other writers to use such pieces in future while practicing rules of citation as well. Academic writing may seem to be very challenging but to some extent people like myself will be encouraged to proceed with studies once the writer have a mastery of the key concepts on how to write an academic paper or thesis. Writing academic papers to an extent inflate weak ideas and obscure poor reasoning.

REFERENCES

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